

Multimedia Tools in Teaching and Learning

*Nur Iffah Hazirah Ahmad Fu'ad, Nurhanis Nor Sam

Faculty of Information Management
Universiti Teknologi MARA (UiTM)
Selangor, Malaysia

*Email: iffah74@gmail.com

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Abstract. Education is a pillar to the development of the countries and is vital to build a brighter future for the nation's teenager as professionals and also citizens which is to prove their ability with the skills to be valued careers. The advancement of the technology, have established multimedia tools to improve the education system. Multimedia is the use of more than one media types with assistance of technology, to improve memorization or comprehension. It is necessary for educators, teachers and students effectively understand utilization multimedia tools that provide significant educational benefits. This paper provides an overview about several types of multimedia tools used in teaching and learning that are helpful in improving educational quality and student performance in academics Present generation in the 21st century is already familiar with gadgets and other technological devices, therefore the educational system should take this opportunity by incorporating multimedia tools into classroom.

Keywords: teaching, learning, types of multimedia tools, effectiveness, advantages

Introduction

Multimedia tools in general may be defined as digital learning resources that aid users in becoming familiar with the representations offered via the use of numerous media components. Multimedia tools are formulated of information and learning activities that are delivered via the use of multiple components such as video, picture, audio, graphic and text using digital learning resources. According to Abd Mukti and P.H.,(2004), educational multimedia applications were more focused on specific goals and comprehensive approaches. Multimedia tools in education are fundamentally comparable to how we study in person and with printed text books, but by using

multimedia tools, we have access to a wider choice of sources. Multimedia educational integrates five fundamental media element kinds into a learning environment, resulting in a strong new tool for educational purposes.

The use of media to promote teaching and learning by engaging with students, motivating them in subject matter and demonstrating the applicability of various learning concepts. Since there are so many free access to number of teaching tools that may be used as learning materials, all educators can offer a variety of methods or approaches for learning to students on a daily basis (Baharuddin et al., 2021). Certain of the tools, such as Quizizz may assists teachers in tracking and measuring the progress of their student performance and understanding regarding the topics. This kind of programme application assists teachers in keeping track of their students and provided them with new tutorial to help them enhance their understanding. Due to the variety of colors and pattern, our brain is rapidly attracted and more engaged when we employ video and visual images. As a result, individuals are better equipped to comprehend the topics concept.

The use of multimedia tools in education allows teachers to stimulate the ultimate results and assists students in applying knowledge gained from written materials such as textbooks. By utilizing multimedia tools, students are able to receive information through media, which motivates them to be more creative and encourages their imaginations.

Types of Multimedia Tools

It seems like multimedia tools are widely use now in teaching and learning as the current situation changes the progressions in education sector worldwide. This is due to the rapid changes in technology forced education sector to revolve continually to ensure all humans get knowledge they deserve fairly and easily. The old trend in educational institutions with isolated audio and visual are now long gone, instead the use of multimedia within the sector grows rapidly as an expansion for the better future. Fortunately, there are variety types of multimedia tools that can be used in teaching and learning nowadays that can be easily access and much more convenient rather than using old-school tools. In its transforming and exchanging operation, the education system should change its teaching methods so that learners actively learn the content, become engaged face to face with the issues, and answer the questions for problem solving. Even so, even though traditional educational methods and curricula are still used in schools, the educational system must change its methods so that students actively participate in educational programs. Therefore, IT applications like multimedia alternatives should be taken into action (Afyouni et al., 2016).

Fundamentally, multimedia can be categorized into two categories – linear and non-linear. Linear multimedia progresses can be control without any navigation control by viewers, for instance cinema presentation meanwhile non-linear multimedia also known as hypermedia content, which presentations can be recorded or live. Recorded presentation allows interactivity via navigation system and live content presentation allows interactivity via interaction with the presenter. As the

definition, there are a lot of multimedia available today that has various purposes to serve its users. In general, multimedia technology for educational purposes can be classified according to whether it is used for teaching or learning (Abdulrahman et al., 2020).

These days, the use of multimedia tools in classroom has become essential as both students and educators have been familiarizing themselves with the tools. Students and educators have been teaching and learning days by days to access information, creating, collaborating and sharing ideas using variety of multimedia tools and electronic devices. Multimedia applications vary accordingly to its functions, ease of navigation, features and systems and designs. Most tools curated in the list below are free and many cater to multiple languages and offer functionalities across multiple categories that can be a helpful tool for parents, educators, students, schools, and school administrators in education sector during this critical time.

Multimedia Tools

Zoom Classroom

According to Singh, et al (2020), Zoom is one of the top popular video conferencing applications today. The participant does not need to go through the hassle of registering into Zoom in order to join an online meeting room. Technically, Zoom has numerous functions that enable educators to engage students in virtual meetings such as allow multiple participants, recording, presenting, working on whiteboard and so many more. Zoom, a video conferencing tool, has recently become extremely popular due to its great features that allow hundreds video participants and up to 49 videos on screen (Singh, et al, 2020). Based on these numerous features of Zoom, it is expected that Zoom rose to be one of the popular multimedia tools in education.

Google Meet

Google Meet is a free virtual meeting accessed by Gmail. In order to use this tool, users must have Gmail account first. It is an easy tool to navigate as most students and educators have personal email thus, making it top multimedia tool in Malaysia. In fact, all around the globe, - business, schools and other users find Google Meet is an easy app that allow them to stay connected and get work done (Singh, et al, 2020). Mostly because of the app's security operators are turned on by default – making it easier to ensure participants' protection.

TED-Ed

For many decades, video content has been used to support the motivation and learning of students in higher education (Russell, 2016). Students entering university are viewed as digital natives who benefit from the incorporation of digital technology in the learning environment, with younger students reporting greater enjoyment when video is used as a teaching tool in class (Russell, 2016). This website tool allows democratizing access to information, both for educators and students especially in

higher education. Moreover, according to Russell (2016), TED-Ed is an excellent tool for supporting teaching practice in a new model of education that allows students to learn what they want, when they want, and at their own pace.

Canva for education

Canva for education is a powerful design tool that allows teachers and students to create visually stunning designs for any subject or age level. According to (Yundayani et al., 2019), visuals in the classroom, including Canva, can serve a variety of purposes, including: 1) making abstract ideas concrete; 2) motivating students; 3) giving direct attention; and 4) repeating information. It enables its users to create their own designs from scratch, or choose from ready-made templates with high resolutions and finest quality educational templates. Interesting and colourful visuals does attract students' attentions more than just words.

Quizizz

This multimedia is designed to engage learning platform where users can customize their own quizzes, lessons, presentations and even flashcards not only for students but everyone including employees, families and many more. The navigation system is good enough that it has become one of the most popular platforms used by many school teachers in this country designated for quizzes, pre-test reviews and so on. The app uses Q-nickname format was used, and these nicknames were not shared with anyone, - with a lot of visuals and memes, making it more enjoyable for students (Göksün and Gürsoy, 2019).

Prezi

Prezi is a presentation app known mostly for its style of zoom in navigation and a "slideless" design, with the core concept of creating presentations that stays connected to every section and the presenter can choose to zoom in and navigate between every slide seamlessly. Since the presentations are stored online, the author of a presentation can grants others access not only to view the presentation, but also to edit it. This means that students can collaborate even if they are not in the same room or even online at the same time (Strasser, 2014). The unique style of presentation does really stand out as it seems complex, but this app is really easy to use which just really intriguing to students.

Kahoot!

This one almost has the same functions to Quizizz but with a bit of a twist, which it is based on game and questions. Through this tool, educators can create their own questionnaires, discussions or even surveys that matched academic lessons' desires. The materials projected in the classroom and questions are answered by students while playing games designated and learning at the same time. According to Göksün and Gürsoy (2019), the impact of using the Kahoot application as a formative assessment tool on the academic achievements of pre-service teachers was reported, as was the effect of the Kahoot application on student retention levels. This platform suits kindergarten level well since it has games for every questionnaire as it promotes

game-based learning system – that increases students’ engagements and creates a dynamic, social and fun educational environment.

Powtoon

In the current era, the learning process that uses digital-based media is indeed very necessary, especially to accommodate the development of learners who are very familiar with the advancement of technology and information (Nurdiansyah et al., 2018). Powtoon designed to capture audiences’ attention by using creative presentations templates which help teachers and educators to ensure maximum information delivery to students. According to Nurdiansyah et al. (2018), using and designing technology or media, in particular, can greatly contribute to effective learning for all students and help them achieve their full potential regardless of innate abilities.

Google Classroom

Google Classroom is a Learning Management System (LMS) for teachers provided by Google. This application serves as a hub for students to communicate, ask questions, and make assignments (Sudarsana et al., 2019). Classroom can be used by educators to streamline assignments, boost collaboration, and foster communication. Sudarsana (2019), stated that in today's increasingly digital world, Google Classroom assists digital learners in facilitating online learning. Users can use Classroom tools such as Gmail, Google Docs and Google Calendar.

SelfCAD

According to Gouri (2020), to promote learning, students are provided with curriculum. There are various types of tech-based tools available for use in the classroom that are specifically designed to encourage, enhance, and manage learning. SelfCAD is a cloud-based software package for students as it is easy to use, yet it provides an authentic, ‘real-world’ 3D design experience. It provides a database complete 3D printable design, making thousands of 3D objects available for immediate 3D printing. It is a powerful and effective tool for education sector. Due to our higher sensory stimulation as we watch, listen, explore, and learn by doing simultaneously during the teaching learning process through digitalization, our learning is sustained for a longer period of time (Gouri, 2020).

Differences for Each Tools

Most of these tools have similar functions but each tool has their own distinct differences which makes every tool special on their own. The differences for each tool are listed as below;

Zoom Classroom vs Google Meet

First of all, Zoom's interface security is easily penetrated. Zoom is plagued by a slew of security and privacy issues, which they are attempting to address with regular updates. Although Zoom has fixed several security flaws, it will take time for users to regain trust (Singh, et al, 2020). The security operators in Google Meet are enabled by default – in most cases, users are not required to ensure that adequate safeguards are in place. Google Meet combines a number of anti-abuse safeguards to keep users' meetings safe. Singh, et al, (2020) stated that, these include anti-hijacking safeguards for meetings site as well as dial-ins. Among all these differences, both apps have their own advantages and disadvantages; it is all depend on the users' preferences.

Quizizz vs Kahoot!

There are many similarities between the two platforms but each has slight difference focus whereby Kahoot is teacher directed as it displays questions and answers on teacher's device, meanwhile Quizizz is based on students direct, as it displays all the information on student's device. According to Göksün and Gürsoy (2019), when compared the both activities with the Kahoot application had a higher positive influence on academic success and student engagement, although being statistically insignificant. In terms of academic accomplishment, Quizizz application was lower than that of the control group's instruction technique.

Prezi vs Canva

Prezi is used mainly for presentations slides, making students working in groups can create group presentations in which each student can edit the presentation (Strasser, 2014) meanwhile, Canva is able to create multiple designs including presentations, posters, info-graphics, book covers, websites, and so many more. Canva provides a moment experience for students to engage in the creative process, allowing them to repeat the material by recalling past knowledge (Yundayani et al, 2019). Not only that, users are able to sign in using official students or educator emails – granting premium access in the app meanwhile with Prezi, users only get various access if only they paid for premium fees.

TED-ed vs Google Classroom

Google Classroom is free to download, but it must be installed at the level of educational institutions contains many popular Google applications such as Gmail, Google Calendar, and Google Drive, which can be accessed by anyone (Sudarsana, 2019) meanwhile TED-ed is rarely used in Malaysia but very popular among educators overseas. TED-ed allows students to “dig-deeper” – synthesize material from the video, further readings as well critically analyze diverse points of views from classmates (Russell, 2016) meanwhile Google Classroom is linked specific to the teacher's workspace which save more time.

Self-CAD vs Powtoon

PowToon, as one of the multimedia programmes that may be used as a learning medium, has numerous advantages, including a very intriguing animated feature that includes handwritten animation and animated cartoons (Nurdiansyah et al, 2018).

PowToon is easily made on its website, and the output can be utilized offline as multimedia making this tool one of the top choices for local educators. On the other side, self-CAD is an online 3D designing software that allows audiences to watch 3D videos as it is able to render, model, sculpt, draw and even sketch on their own. Gouri (2020) said there are numerous types of tech-based tools available for use in the classroom that are expressly designed to encourage, enhance, and manage learning – this software sure is one of the top choices for arts educators who wanted to attract students' attention.

Every multimedia tool has its' own specialty that attracts users as most of them have distinct differences and is useful according to users' needs. As Gouri (2019) stated that there are a variety of tech-based tools available for use in the classroom that are expressly developed for encouraging, augmenting, and managing learning process that benefitted both educators and students. Therefore, it is advisable for users to identify the need of what they wanted to create first, only then it is easy to choose the best and suitable multimedia tool for them as every tool differs from each other. Media training is a method for presenting comprehensive training and is a natural part of the learning and educational technology process, but not the entire process (Afyouni et al, 2016) – even so, traditional learning process is still very much needed.

Effectiveness of Multimedia Tools in Education

In general multimedia learning is a method in which learners are exposed to the use of images, audio such as video and animation. Multimedia learning tools may be utilized to assist students in comprehending the text by utilizing prior knowledge and new terminology. Further, the variety of components in multimedia tools can aid students in their learning process and enhance their enthusiasm to study (Abdul Samat & Abdul Aziz., 2020). Besides, the application of multimedia tools in learning and teaching may also improve memory retention, learning accomplishment and satisfaction with the material presented to students on the material provided. There is a findings shows primary students spend around 60% whilst high school and college students spend 90% of their time listening to lectures. As a results, after two months, only half of the students could recall the lesson, demonstrating that this learning technique is not beneficial and that a new approach should be used rather than concentrating solely on auditory learning and lectures. As a contrary, our educational system must devise new techniques and implement multimedia teaching and learning tools.

According to the research of Afyouni et al. (2016), the findings of the study show that learning through multimedia tools is far superior to the traditional technique known as lecture class. It has the abilities to create learning more interesting and to engage students in the learning environment. Apart from that, multimedia capabilities allow students to actively participate with course while learning, while somehow enjoying visual representation and audio components for further attractiveness. As a consequence, it elevates the attitude and motivates students to better comprehend the

lecture and complete their assigned tasks. For example, a teacher may customize their own teaching material in video approaches with via combination of audio, images and text. The teacher may create step by step video demonstrating how to work through the question. So through this video student be able to comprehend the topic more effectively. Video content is one of the methods that able to reach students faster since it significantly help in memory improvement by facilitating thinking and enables them to quickly memorize the content (Baharuddin et al., 2019a). It also allows teachers to be more creative when designing learning materials and to enhance their teaching methods by analyzing student performance and effectiveness from the previous teaching methods.

In addition, multimedia tools can improve engagement between teachers and students and make the learning process more goals-oriented (Almarabeh et al., 2015). With the variety of multimedia tools it able to assist the teachers to deliver the information to the students, especially during current epidemic. To maintain learning continuity, teachers and educators must be adaptive by using the hybrid or online distance learning approach. For example, the teachers may create their own teaching material by using slide presentations or record their lessons for future student reference. As we all know, internet connection is the major issue in online learning, therefore by using multimedia tools everyone able to learn since students may learn the topics at their own available time and place. Aside from that, multimedia tools may help teachers keep track of their student's performance through videoconferencing such as the Google Meet or Webex application. These applications assists students in gaining a better understanding of a topic that is unclear to them and receiving an answer at the same time, as well as being able to exchange responses to questions with teachers in real time. Hence, no one will missed out on learning the topic and will be able to comprehend the subject or topic. Besides, all students are encouraged to share their thoughts and opinion on the topic, which will develop their critical thinking skills and enrich their learning experience.

In a nutshell, multimedia tools in teaching and learning help to enhance student prior knowledge since the appealing features of the multimedia tools might allow them to boost their stimulation to the learning process. This can assist both students and teachers enhance the quality of their education while also motivating students to study hard in order to get a higher grade and performance in the respective subject. Learning is a difficult journey if teachers continue to use old methods. As a result, teachers must understand how to use multimedia tools in the classroom, especially in the 21st century. Advanced of technology brought the students to a new way of thinking so the teachers should be able to keep up with the students in order to improve teaching and learning quality. By fully utilize multimedia tools in the classroom, students are able to discover their latent potential and enhance their ability, allowing both teachers and students to raise their self-confidence due to the efficacy of this technique. It also helps students develop their thinking and reasoning skills, which will allow them to be more creative. After all, multimedia tools are a highly successful approach for both the teachers and the students in a positive way.

Advantages of Multimedia Tools in Education

The advancement of technology has enabled individuals to be more self-sufficient and benefit in a variety of ways, including the education system. People may use technology to create multimedia tools that assist in the learning process. Multimedia tools are the ideal complement to the 3Cs, which stands for creativity, communication, collaboration and critical thinking. Using multimedia tools will stimulate the attention of both teachers and students, allowing them to receive training, obtain and manage how to use multimedia resources for educational contents. There are several advantages and benefit that multimedia brings to the education.

Firstly, it may benefit the students with online material that the teachers may assist them in accessing via the internet. The teacher would be able to educate the students how to utilize the tools effectively, particularly for learning purposes. Students would be able to identify how and which information would be beneficial to them by participating in multimedia activities. For their learning references, the teacher can also aid students by using education web search engines such as Google Scholar or JSTOR. The multimedia technology class situated in a new-type online classroom aims integration of teaching and learning and offers students with additional incentives, with teachers' guidance driving students' cognitive patterns and stimulating students' emotions (Xu,2010). As a result, it may assist students in expressing their prior knowledge and offer them with numerous learning opportunities. By fully utilizing the functions of multimedia tools, students will be able to explore more, encouraging them to broaden their understanding of the subject. Learning through multimedia is highly exciting since students no longer have to spend their time focused on attempting to interpret a textbook that is full of words and simply listening to the teachers' lectures. For example, as we all know history is a difficult subject that student must pass, yet it might be tiresome for students because it is so full of stories. Learning history in the conventional method may weary the students, and the chance of them becoming less focused in the lecture is extremely high. However due to the advancement of multimedia technologies, the teacher may assign a task to the student to look for information relevant to the topic and develop their own learning material. As they have prepared themselves, they will definitely employ a variety of multimedia element to enable them understand the concepts. Thus, multimedia tools have motivated students' in creative and positive thinking.

Next, using multimedia tools is very cost effective because it minimizes the amount of time spent studying. Moreover, by utilizing multimedia tools, it offers a logistical benefit in that which the teacher's material can be distributed more conveniently and economically. This ensures that everyone receives the same learning material, and teachers may using a specific application to offer all learning materials. For example, the teacher may utilize Google Classroom to provide all formative assessments that are solely accessible to her students. Hence, the students may quickly access the application and revise the material on their own at home. The teachers is no longer the centre of attention as the source of knowledge, but rather

serves as a facilitator, providing them with guidance and instructions, information resources and support throughout the learning process. Instead of having paper to share details of information, it would be preferable to use an application so that students do not have any excuses such as losing the paper and having to reprint or redo due to their negligence. Aside from that, the teacher should be able to maximize the tool so that all of the features given may assist both teacher and the students. Traditional methods include the use of paper and books, which is inefficient for students; thus, we should switch to multimedia tools for examinations and quizzes, especially during this online distance learning due to the pandemic restriction. As the results, the teacher can save money on written quizzes and material learning.

Last but not least, using multimedia tools may help the student and teacher be more flexible in terms of time and place. Learning and teaching may be made more pleasant and enjoyable by using multimedia tools. Learning by using multimedia tools encourages the students to be more inventive in their classrooms (Baharuddin et al., 2020). It will stimulate creativity and ability in students, allowing them to feel confident in their capacity to design their own learning materials, evaluate, browse information and sharing their knowledge to classmates. Obviously, this approach of learning and teaching method may engage the students and empower them to develop and design their own learning material instead of absorbing representations provided by others. After all, multimedia tools enable students to engage deep reflective thinking and master basic skills such as writing and problem solving.

Conclusion

Multimedia tools have been proven to be beneficial in delivering educational learning materials. Since the late 1980s, the progress of multimedia applications in the education sector has been demonstrated. Since the rapid growth of technology, particularly in multimedia applications, the education sector has gradually become more dependent on multimedia tools. Multimedia tools combine important elements such as texts, images, audios, videos, animations and user control all into one, making it easier, more engaging and effective by saving time. This due to the fact that multimedia tools assist students get a deeper understanding since multimedia applications engage all of the senses, including verbal listening and visual displays of knowledge, enabling the human brain to assimilate the information more easily. On top of that, students have access to a wide range of information through the use of electronic devices, mainly communication gadgets that are fully equipped, making it easier for students to explore for any information they require. Discussions sessions are simpler to have these days since teachers may encourage students to contribute knowledge, which boosts student's confidence in speaking in front of a large group. Apart from these benefits, there are definitely some drawbacks, such as students as being agitated when they do not understand a topic since teachers or lectures are not always accessible to aid them, which may drive them to work on their problem independently without guidance. Above all, there is no doubt that multimedia tools

have a beneficial influence for educational purposes and have been shown to greatly assist educators and students.

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